

http://plugin28.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

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1 <!doctype html>
2 <html lang="pt-PT" prefix="og: http://ogp.me/ns#">
3
4 <head>
5     <meta charset="UTF-8">
6     <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, in
7     <link rel="profile" href="http://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9     <title>Marketing Digital Tools &#8211; Agência de Mar
10 <!-- Premmerce SEO for WooCommerce -->
11 <meta property="og:locale" content="pt_PT" />
12 <meta property="og:type" content="website" />
13 <meta property="og:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools &#
14 <meta property="og:description" content="Agência de Marketing
15 <meta property="og:url" content="http://plugin28.marketingdigi
16 <meta property="og:site_name" content="Marketing Digital Tools
17 <meta name="twitter:title" content="Marketing Digital Tools &#
18 <meta name="twitter:description" content="Agência de Marketing
19 <meta name="twitter:site" content="@mktdigitaltools" />
20 <script type="application/ld+json">{"@context":"https://scheme
21 <!-- /Premmerce SEO for WooCommerce -->
22 <link rel="dns-prefetch" href="//s.w.org" />
23 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
24 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
25     <script type="text/javascript">
26         window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl":"https://\s.
27         !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("ca
28     </script>
29     <style type="text/css">
30     img.wp-smiley,
31     img.emoji {
32         display: inline !important;
33         border: none !important;
34         box-shadow: none !important;
35         height: 1em !important;
36         width: 1em !important;
37         margin: 0 .07em !important;
38         vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
39         background: none !important;
40         padding: 0 !important;
41     }
42 </style>
43     <link rel='stylesheet' id='wp-block-library-css' href='ht
44 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wc-block-style-css' href='http://g
45 <link rel='stylesheet' id='dashicons-css' href='http://plugi
46 <link rel='stylesheet' id='everest-forms-general-css' href='f
47 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-layout-css' href='http
48 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-smallscreen-css' href=
49 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-general-css' href='htt
50 <style id='woocommerce-inline-inline-css' type='text/css'>
51 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
52 </style>
53 <link rel='stylesheet' id='font-awesome-css' href='http://pl
54 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-style-css' href='http://plug
55 <style id='zakra-style-inline-css' type='text/css'>
56 @media (min-width: 1200px) { .tg-container{max-width: 1200px;} }
57 .tg-primary-menu > div ul li a{font-family: -apple-system, bli
58 </style>
59 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-woocommerce-style-css' href=
60 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-css' href='http://
61 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-animations-css' href='ht
62 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-frontend-css' href='http
63 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-global-css' href='http://
64 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-post-24-css' href='http:
65 <link rel='stylesheet' id='google-fonts-1-css' href='https://
66 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-shared-0-css' href=

```

Organization

All (1)

Organization	0 ERROS	2 AVISOS
@type	Organization	
url	http://plugin28.marketingdigitaltools.com/	
name	Marketing Digital Tools	
sameAs	https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/	
sameAs	https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools	
sameAs	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFiw/featured	
sameAs	https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools	
sameAs	https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/	
email	info@marketingdigitaltools.com	
telephone	+351913824934	
openingHours	Mo-Fr 09:00-18:00 (A propriedade <i>openingHours</i> não é reconhecida pelo Google para um objeto do tipo <i>Organization</i> .)	
paymentAccepted	Credit Card (A propriedade <i>paymentAccepted</i> não é reconhecida pelo Google para um objeto do tipo <i>Organization</i> .)	
address		
@type	PostalAddress	
name	Rua de Santo António de Contumil, 651 Porto 4350-291 Porto Portugal	